

Beyond the Breaking Point: Examining Burnout's Roots in Work Culture and Personal Well-Being. A Study on Young Adults

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Abstract: This study investigates the prevalence and determinants of burnout among young adult employees in Poland, focusing on a sample of 166 respondents surveyed via Google Forms. Using the Polish adaptation of the Maslach Burnout Inventory, we analyzed three dimensions of burnout: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal accomplishment. Six demographic variables were considered, age, gender, education level, monthly salary, civil status, and family structure, with only the civil status of individuals being significantly linked to burnout. Individuals who did not have a partner reported higher burnout than those living with a partner, highlighting the importance of social factors in reducing burnout. Beyond this, prioritizing job satisfaction over salary emerged as a significant factor, with individuals who prioritized that reported lower burnout. Perceived salary adequacy, as opposed to the actual monthly salary, and perceived physical health correlated significantly with reduced burnout levels, emphasizing the impact of financial and health perceptions on employee well-being. Additionally, perceptions of managerial fairness and freedom of expression significantly influenced burnout, underlining the importance of supportive workplace environments. Overall, the results suggest that while most demographic factors may not significantly influence burnout, social factors, subjective evaluations of job, and organizational culture play a crucial role as indicators of employee mental health. This research underscores the need for organizations to foster environments that promote satisfaction, fairness, and open communication to mitigate burnout risks among young employees.

Keywords: Burnout Syndrome, Work Culture, Personal Well-Being, Young Adults.

Além do Ponto de Ruptura: Examinando as Raízes do Burnout na Cultura de Trabalho e no Bem-Estar Pessoal. Um Estudo sobre Jovens Adultos

Resumo: Este estudo investiga a prevalência e os determinantes do *burnout* entre jovens adultos empregados na Polônia, com foco em uma amostra de 166 respondentes, que participaram de uma pesquisa realizada por meio do Google Forms. Utilizando a adaptação polonesa do Maslach Burnout Inventory, foram analisadas três dimensões do *burnout*: exaustão emocional, despersonalização e realização pessoal. Seis variáveis demográficas foram consideradas: idade, sexo, nível de escolaridade, salário mensal, estado civil e estrutura familiar. Apenas o estado civil dos indivíduos se mostrou significativamente relacionado ao *burnout*. Indivíduos sem parceiro relataram níveis mais elevados de *burnout* em comparação com aqueles que viviam com um parceiro, destacando a importância dos fatores sociais na redução do *burnout*. Além disso, a priorização da satisfação no trabalho em relação ao salário emergiu como um fator significativo, com os indivíduos que priorizaram isso a revelar menores níveis de *burnout*. A percepção de adequação salarial, ao contrário do salário mensal real, e a percepção de saúde física correlacionaram-se significativamente com níveis reduzidos de *burnout*, enfatizando o impacto das percepções financeiras e de saúde no bem-estar. Adicionalmente, a percepção de justiça gerencial e a liberdade de expressão influenciaram significativamente o burnout, destacando a importância de ambientes de trabalho que ofereçam apoio. Em geral, os resultados sugerem que, embora a maioria dos fatores demográficos não influencie significativamente o *burnout*, fatores sociais, avaliações subjetivas do trabalho e a cultura organizacional desempenham um papel crucial como indicadores da saúde mental dos empregados. Esta pesquisa sublinha a necessidade de as organizações promoverem ambientes que incentivem a satisfação, a justiça e a comunicação aberta para mitigar os riscos de *burnout* entre os jovens empregados.

Palavras-chave: Síndrome de *Burnout*, Cultura de Trabalho, Bem-Estar Pessoal, Jovens Adultos.

1. Introduction

Burnout is a complex phenomenon arising from a combination of organizational and personal factors, with considerable consequences for both individual health and organizational performance. Recently, burnout has become a prominent area of study within work and organizational psychology, as well as public and mental healthcare. Its significance has been emphasized by its inclusion in the ICD-10 (International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems) classification of diseases, and its symptoms closely align with those seen in occupational neurasthenia (Ślęzyk & Sobol, 2012). While traditionally attributed primarily to personality traits, research increasingly underscores the role of organizational factors in burnout. For example, Bakker et. al., 2004, highlight the interactions between work-related and individual personality factors in the development of burnout.

While professional work can provide satisfaction, fulfillment, and well-being, it can also be a source of chronic stress, frustration, and dissatisfaction, which contribute to burnout. The syndrome, first characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment, is particularly prevalent in interpersonal professions such as healthcare, social services, and education. Prolonged emotional exhaustion due to excessive mental and physical demands can erode job satisfaction, increasing the risk of burnout (Schaufeli & Taris, 2005).

Multiple work-related factors can predict burnout including a lack of support from supervisors and colleagues (Maslach et. al., 2001; Maslach & Leiter, 2008; Leiter & Maslach, 2014), excessive workload (Maslach et al., 2001; Demerouti et al., 2001; Maslach & Leiter, 2008), workplace conflicts (Maslach et al., 2001), work-life conflicts (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985), and lack of control over one's responsibilities. In teaching, for instance, negative organizational culture and poor management elevate burnout risk, as noted by Ingersoll, 2001. Moreover, a negative organizational climate marked by low trust, conflict, and unpredictability contributes to burnout (Leiter et al., 2014). Limited tolerance for diversity, including cultural, religious, or ideological differences, further elevates burnout risk as it negatively affects the workplace environment and employee well-being.

Studies indicate that lower income levels increase burnout risk due to financial stress (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). Employees who lack opportunities for professional growth are also more vulnerable to burnout (Maslach et al., 2001), as are those working in environments with unclear goals or ineffective personnel policies, which exacerbate the risk (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). Conversely, organizations that promote innovation, trust, and open communication are less susceptible to burnout, as a supportive workplace culture enhances employee well-being (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). Positive interpersonal interactions and open communication across all hierarchical levels also reduce burnout risk (Jones & George, 1998). Employees who feel valued and able to express their views freely report a lower likelihood of experiencing burnout (Haver et al., 2017).

The focus on individual characteristics in burnout research often emphasizes personality traits, framing burnout as a personal issue. Terelak, 2001, highlights attributes like passivity, low self-esteem, defensiveness, and emotional immaturity as contributors. Cherniss, 1992, argues that burnout arises from competency gaps within workplace settings, while Şek ,2009, contends that it results from ineffective responses to stress rather than stress itself.

Research suggests burnout's roots lie in social and organizational environments rather than within individuals alone. Pines et. al., 2009, argues that burnout stems from unfulfilled searches for meaning in life, and negative emotionality plays a role in susceptibility, with high nervous reactivity heightening risk (Łosiak, 2008). Studies by Demerouti et. al. (2001), link type A personality traits (high ambition, competitiveness, and impatience) with burnout, especially under high-stress conditions. Schaufeli et al. (2009), further confirm this association, indicating that workaholic tendencies among type A personalities elevate burnout risk.

Socioeconomic factors, including financial well-being and social support, are also significant in understanding burnout. Research highlights that economic hardship and low socioeconomic status contribute to burnout and depression risk (Bianchi & Schonfeld, 2015). Individuals with limited material and social resources face elevated work-related stress and lower access to support networks, increasing burnout vulnerability (Widerszal-Bazyl & Cieślak, 2000). Gendered economic disadvantages expose women to a heightened risk of burnout, particularly those who are single or supporting children.

The main goal of this research is to explore the relationship between burnout and various organizational and socioeconomic factors among young adult employees. In addition to insights from organizational psychology and occupational health, burnout is increasingly being investigated through the lens of broader critical and interdisciplinary frameworks. Psychosocial risk studies, for instance, explore how work-related suffering is shaped not only by task-related stressors but by organizational injustice, systemic invisibility of emotional labor, and the erosion of subjectivity in high-demand environments (Dejours, 2009; Eurofound & EU-OSHA, 2014). Critical management studies, on the other hand, challenge the ideological underpinnings of contemporary managerial practices, particularly the normalization of overwork, the instrumentalization of identity, and the masking of workplace alienation under discourses of "engagement" and "resilience" (Alvesson & Willmott, 2003; Fleming, 2017). From the perspective of work psychodynamics, burnout is not merely an outcome of work overload but a symptom of deeper conflicts between one's desire for meaning and the symbolic violence embedded in managerial discourse (Clot, 2010; Dejours, 1998). These views align with recent socio-political critiques of affective labor and emotional capitalism (Hochschild, 1983; Illouz, 2007), which argue that the commodification of emotion and self in the workplace accelerates psychic exhaustion. Taken together, these perspectives reframe burnout as a socially produced phenomenon- less a failure of personal adaptation and more a consequence of structural contradictions, normative control, and misrecognized suffering. Integrating such critical and psychodynamic perspectives may offer a more holistic and justice-oriented understanding of burnout in contemporary work cultures.

By analyzing elements such as perceived salary adequacy, perceived fairness in management, subjective physical health, and opportunities for self-expression in workplace, this study seeks to identify key predictors of burnout. The findings aim to contribute to a more nuanced understanding of burnout's roots, moving beyond traditional personality-based explanations to highlight the roles of financial security, workplace inclusivity, and managerial support. This research seeks to inform strategies that can mitigate burnout risk and foster healthier, more resilient work environments for young professionals.

2. Burnout Syndrome

The concept of burnout was first introduced by Freudenberger in 1974. He defined emotional exhaustion as a decrease in motivation and a decline in commitment to work. The concept gained prominence in literature through the works of Maslach and Leiter during the decade of 1990. According to Maslach and Leiter (2007), burnout syndrome manifests as a cynical attitude toward work as feelings of inadequacy increase, finally leading to a sense of exhaustion.

Burnout syndrome consists of three components: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and diminished personal accomplishment (Vidotti et al., 2018). The initial symptom observed in individuals experiencing burnout was the depletion of emotional resources. These individuals established sharp boundaries in their relationships with others and became indifferent to the social groups to which they belong (American Thoracic Society, 2016). Aware of these changes, they increasingly felt inadequate due to nostalgia for past successes, leading them to believe they can no longer contribute to their organization (Ardıç & Polatçı, 2008, p. 71).

The primary cause of emotional exhaustion is the growing burden of tasks and responsibilities in the workplace (Akçamete et al., 2006). Over time, individuals exposed to a heavy workload tend to experience cumulative fatigue and a corresponding decline in their life energy. In other words, those who believe they can manage more work may feel pressured and develop negative thoughts about their work life (Yıldız, 2015).

As individuals exhaust their emotional resources, they tend to adopt negative attitudes toward others they interact with at work, a phenomenon referred to as depersonalization (Nurka & Males-Bilic, 2014). At this stage, the level of burnout syndrome increases. Individuals may isolate themselves from others, attempting to avoid experiences they believe could negatively impact them. This attitude contradicts the collaboration essential for productivity in contemporary businesses, leading to a decline in personal performance (Dalkılıç, 2014).

As individuals become aware of their decreasing performance, they start to feel inadequate with each subjective evaluation. This stage, termed "reduced personal accomplishment", is characterized by dissatisfaction with their work performance (Maslach & Jackson, 1981). With the belief that they cannot cope with the challenges they face in their work life; they begin to hold themselves responsible for this inadequacy. Therefore, the trust that others in their groups have in them may also diminish (Dalkılıç, 2014).

Burnout severely impacts an individual's personal life and well-being. Salvagioni et al. (2017), found associations between burnout and both mental and physical health problems, including depression and chronic fatigue. Melchior et al., 2017, reported that burnout increases risks for cardiovascular diseases, hypertension, and digestive disorders. Burnout-induced chronic stress can compromise immune and other body systems (Demerouti et al., 2001). Burnout also affects family dynamics, often leading to irritability, frustration, and disengagement. Maslach et al. (2001) highlight how burnout diminishes life satisfaction, leaving individuals feeling helpless, apathetic and unfulfilled.

Burnout also has a profoundly negative impact on organizations, detrimentally affecting both productivity and overall economic outcomes. Studies have shown that burnout significantly lowers employee efficiency and productivity, as it diminishes motivation, commitment, and trust; for instance, Maslach and Leiter (1997), noted this decline in productivity, while Bakker et al. (2004) observed that burnout impairs task performance, concentration, and decision-making, further reducing operational efficiency.

Moreover, burnout is strongly linked to increased absenteeism and turnover, as affected employees are more likely to take sick leave or resign, which subsequently raises recruitment and training costs (Maslach et al., 2001). Health-related expenses also rise as burnout contributes to issues like depression and cardiovascular disease, leading to additional medical costs (Melamed et al., 2006). The erosion of employee loyalty and commitment is another critical consequence, with burnout fostering negativity toward work and reducing job satisfaction (Schaufeli & Salanova, 2007). Additionally, burnout can compromise customer service quality, especially among customer-facing employees, which not only impacts service delivery but can also harm customer relationships and the organization's reputation (Bakker et. al., 2005).

Collectively, these impacts increase organizational costs and decrease competitiveness (Şek, 2009; Maslach & Leiter, 2010). Consequently, preventing burnout and fostering a supportive work environment are essential strategies for maintaining sustainable organizational performance and growth.

3. Data Collection, Processing and Analysis

The survey was sent using Google Forms in December 2023 using various distribution channels (social media, professional e-mails) to potential responders, which belonged to a target audience of young adult employees below the age of 35 years, mostly of Polish background. This group of subjects tend to be in the earlier part of their career, which makes this study relevant in terms of understanding burnout in the emerging workforce. This demographic also tends to be more familiar with digital technologies, making them accessible and responsive to surveys collected through internet platforms. By targeting mainly Polish subjects, the study can help understand the challenges facing young professionals in Poland, which can be used to design targeted solutions. The data-collection process was done with respect to all ethical concerns, including anonymity. We obtained 166 responses, of which 146 were kept for analysis after data cleaning.

We used the Polish language adaptation of the MBI - Maslach Burnout Inventory, consisting of twenty-two questions divided into three domains: 9 questions related to emotional exhaustion (EE), 5 questions related to depersonalization (DEP), and 8 questions related to personal accomplishment (PA). Four responses (ordinal variable) were available for each of the questions: very often (0), sometimes (1), rarely (2), never (3). While coding, the answers to the PA questions were flipped -- the larger the value, the higher the MBI Maslach Burnout result. The sum of answers could be then anywhere between 0 to 66 across all of them, between 0 and 27 for the EE domain, between 0 and 15 for the DEP domain, and between 0 and 24 for the PA domain. To allow a comparison between the domain scores and a total that represents all three domains equally, we first computed the average value of the answer for each domain, (minimum is 0, and the maximum is 3), and then computed the total score as the average of the three domain scores. These scores, henceforth referred to as EE, DEP, PA and total MBI scores or variables, were then used as dependent variables for statistical analyses.

The original MBI questionnaire consists of responses on a 7-point Likert scale, whereas our adaptation uses a 4-point Likert scale. The 4-point scale is simpler and faster for respondents to reply, since there are fewer choices. Additionally, with an even number of options, participants are forced to make a non-neutral choice, minimizing fence-sitting (phenomenon where respondents make largely neutral choices). However, the reduced number of options can lead to a potentially biased outcome if respondents feel neutral

about certain questions. Additionally, a 4-point Likert scale reduced reliability (internal consistency) as the responses are less nuanced. For this reason, we performed an internal consistency test using Cronbach's alpha on the responses. The Google Form contained additional questions that aimed to obtain information about the socio-economic status of the respondents. These questions, with response coding in parentheses, were: age (quantitative variable), gender as in ID card (nominal variable – female/male), education (ordinal variable, ranging from vocational college to PhD), net monthly salary range (ordinal variable, with ranges from 0-1000 PLN to >7000 PLN), civil status (ordinal variable with options – no partner, with the partner but living separately, married or living with a partner in the same household – assuming strong correlation of civil and relationship status to loneliness), having children (binary variable – no/yes), form of work (ordinal variable with options – fully remote, hybrid, fully on-site – assuming strong correlation of social isolation to type of work), the length of the current employment (quantitative variable), sector of work (nominal variable, open question). The socioeconomical variables were used for descriptive statistics and were treated as independent variables for analyses.

Additional questions used in the survey concerned the following questions, all of which were subjective, and whose responses were treated on an ordinal scale: importance of earnings vs. importance of work satisfaction (5-point scale), feeling about the adequacy of earnings (3-point scale), personal sense of physical health (5-point scale), assessment of the manager in terms of justness towards employees (5-point scale), and assessment of the freedom to express different opinions about work or private life (3-point scale). For the simplicity of analysis and interpretation, the answers to these questions were arranged in such a way that the *more positive* the answer the higher they are on the scale. The above-mentioned questions were also treated as independent variables.

The data was cleaned, and the answers were coded using Microsoft Excel. For analyzing the age variable (quantitative), we performed linear regression analyses between the four MBI scores (EE, DEP, PA and Total) and age using Scipy implemented in Python. In the case of all other variables, we first performed the assumptions tests of normality (Shapiro Wilk) and homogeneity of variance (Levene's test) of the independent variables with Scipy to determine whether we should use ANOVA F-test or the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis H-test. The F- and H-tests were also performed with Scipy. Finally, the post-hoc testing (standard t-tests in case of significant parametric F-testing and Dunn z-tests in case of significant non-parametric H-testing) was done using JASP with Bonferroni corrections for multiple comparisons.

4. Results

Our sample consisted of 146 participants, with an average age of 24.21 years (std = 3.45). Of them, 38 (26%) were male and 108 (74%) were female. In terms of education level, 67 (46%) participants completed high school, 34 (23%) participants completed Bachelor's, 37 (25%) participants had completed their Master's, and 6 (4%) participants had a doctoral degree. In terms of their civil status, 65 (44%) subjects reported not being in a relationship, 31 (21%) subjects reported being in a relationship but living separately, and 50 (34%) subjects reported being in a relationship and living with their partner. 137 (94%) subjects reported not having children and 9 (6%) reported having at least one child.

Since our adaptation of the MBI questionnaire uses a 4-point Likert scale instead of the typical 7-point Likert scale, we computed the internal consistency using Cronbach's

alpha on the responses, which demonstrated excellent reliability, with an alpha of 0.902 (95% CI [0.877, 0.924]) across all items. The decision to use a 4-point Likert scale was based on the need for simplicity and ease of completion, what was deemed sufficient for capturing the key attitudes and opinions relevant to this study.

The ANOVA F test and the Kruskal-Wallis H test were employed to identify the relationships between the subdimensions of burnout syndrome and demographic variables. The results obtained are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The Relationship Between Scores and Demographic Variables Using ANOVA F Test or Non-Parametric Kruskal-Wallis H Test

		N	Total		EE		DEP		PA	
			Mean (std)	Statistic (p-value)						
Gender	Females	108	1.44 (0.56)	F = 0.16 (0.69)	1.92 (0.66)	H = 0.75 (0.39)	1.26 (0.83)	H = 0.04 (0.84)	1.15 (0.57)	H = 0.52 (0.47)
	Males	38	1.4 (0.58)		1.77 (0.77)		1.21 (0.70)		1.22 (0.63)	
Education	Vocational	2	1.35 (0.03)	F = 0.92 (0.46)	2.28 (0.55)	H = 3.16 (0.53)	0.70 (0.14)	H = 11.98 (0.02)*	1.06 (0.80)	H = 3.61 (0.46)
	High school	67	1.46 (0.59)		1.85 (0.71)		1.37 (0.83)		1.18 (0.60)	
	Bachelor's	34	1.53 (0.58)		1.92 (0.67)		1.44 (0.76)		1.25 (0.58)	
	Master's	37	1.29 (0.54)		1.82 (0.71)		0.92 (0.73)		1.14 (0.55)	
	Ph. D.	6	1.38 (0.37)		2.31 (0.44)		1.03 (0.32)		0.79 (0.64)	
Salary (net PLN)	0 - 1000	5	1.83 (0.55)	H = 8.87 (0.06)	2.31 (0.52)	H = 8.98 (0.06)	1.24 (0.74)	H = 6.68 (0.15)	1.95 (0.64)	H = 8.68 (0.07)
	1001 - 3000	59	1.51 (0.66)		1.91 (0.75)		1.42 (0.90)		1.21 (0.57)	
	3001 - 5000	61	1.42 (0.46)		1.95 (0.61)		1.20 (0.68)		1.12 (0.60)	
	5001 - 7000	14	1.16 (0.41)		1.51 (0.58)		0.97 (0.76)		0.99 (0.37)	
	> 7000	7	1.09 (0.56)		1.46 (0.84)		0.71 (0.59)		1.09 (0.66)	
Civil status	No partner	65	1.59 (0.54)	F = 4.84 (0.01)*	1.95 (0.64)	H = 0.91 (0.64)	1.52 (0.75)	H = 14.99 (<0.001)*	1.30 (0.61)	H = 5.53 (0.06)
	Partner, living separately	31	1.32 (0.58)		1.85 (0.75)		1.05 (0.75)		1.06 (0.53)	
	Living with partner	50	1.30 (0.55)		1.82 (0.72)		1.02 (0.77)		1.06 (0.57)	
Having children	No	137	1.44 (0.56)	F = 0.10 (0.75)	1.89 (0.69)	H = 0.34 (0.56)	1.24 (0.79)	H = 0.05 (0.83)	1.18 (0.58)	H = 0.24 (0.62)
	Yes	9	1.37 (0.63)		1.75 (0.73)		1.31 (0.93)		1.06 (0.64)	
Form of work	Online	8	1.38 (0.88)	H = 2.27 (0.32)	1.72 (0.98)	H = 0.97 (0.61)	1.12 (1.16)	H = 0.96 (0.62)	1.30 (0.80)	H = 2.70 (0.26)
	Hybrid	24	1.31 (0.60)		1.76 (0.73)		1.18 (0.77)		0.99 (0.64)	
	On-site	114	1.46 (0.53)		1.92 (0.66)		1.27 (0.77)		1.20 (0.56)	
		146	1.43 (0.56)	-----	1.88 (0.69)	-----	1.25 (0.79)	-----	1.17 (0.59)	-----

* Significant relations.

The analysis of burnout scores across various demographic factors indicated no significant gender differences. Total burnout scores for females (Mean = 1.44, SD = 0.56) and males (Mean = 1.40, SD = 0.58) were not significantly different ($F(1, 144) = 0.16, p = 0.69$). Additionally, there were no significant differences found in the specific burnout domains of emotional exhaustion (EE) ($H = 0.75, p = 0.39$), depersonalization (DEP) ($H = 0.04, p = 0.84$), or personal accomplishment (PA) ($H = 0.52, p = 0.47$). These results indicate that gender does not significantly influence burnout scores across EE, DEP, and PA.

Similarly, education level did not demonstrate significant differences in total burnout scores ($F(4, 141) = 0.92, p = 0.46$), in the EE scores ($H = 3.16, p = 0.53$), or in the PA scores ($H = 3.61, p = 0.46$). However, there was a significant relationship between the DEP scores and education levels ($H = 11.98, p = 0.02$). Post-hoc Dunn's z-tests with Bonferroni adjustments identified that individuals with a maximum education level of a Master's degree (mean = 0.92, SD = 0.73) had significantly lower DEP scores than individuals with a maximum education level of High school (mean = 1.37, SD = 0.83; $z = 2.824, p = 0.047$) and individuals with a maximum education level of a Bachelor's degree (mean = 1.44, SD = 0.76; $z = 2.946, p = 0.032$). These findings indicate that while education level significantly impacts DEP scores, it does not significantly impact the scores along other dimensions, suggesting that further research is needed to fully understand the role of the education level and burnout.

Salary level also did not exhibit any significant association with total burnout scores ($H = 8.87, p = 0.06$), EE scores ($H = 8.98, p = 0.06$), DEP scores ($H = 6.68, p = 0.15$) and PA scores ($H = 8.68, p = 0.07$). The dependencies approached significance ($p \sim 0.06$), but did not meet the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that this trend warrants further exploration.

The analysis regarding civil status revealed significant differences in total burnout scores ($F(2, 143) = 4.84, p = 0.01$), and DEP scores ($H = 14.99, p = 0.00$). No significant differences were picked up between civil status and EE scores ($H = 0.91, p = 0.64$) or PA scores ($H = 5.53, p = 0.06$). Post-hoc standard t-tests with Bonferroni corrections for the total scores showed that individuals with no partner (mean = 1.59, SD = 0.54) had significantly higher burnout scores than individuals living with a partner (mean = 1.30, SD = 0.55; $t = 2.832, p = 0.016$). Post-hoc Dunn's z-tests with Bonferroni corrections on DEP scores followed this trend by indicating that individuals with no partner (mean = 1.52, SD = 0.75) had significantly lower scores than individuals in a relationship but living separately (mean = 1.05, SD = 0.75; $z = 2.760, p = 0.017$) and those living with their partners (mean = 1.02, SD = 0.77; $z = 3.551, p = 0.001$). These findings indicate that personal relationships may positively impact individuals in the context of burnout.

In terms of family structure, having children did not significantly impact burnout scores. There were no significant differences in total burnout scores ($F(1, 145) = 0.10, p = 0.75$), in EE scores ($H = 0.34, p = 0.56$), DEP scores ($H = 0.05, p = 0.83$), or PA scores ($H = 0.24, p = 0.62$). These results suggest that the presence or absence of children does not notably affect burnout levels across the measured dimensions.

Finally, when examining the format of work (online, hybrid, or on-site), no significant differences were found in total burnout scores ($H = 2.27, p = 0.32$), in EE scores ($H = 0.97, p = 0.61$), DEP scores ($H = 0.96, p = 0.62$), or PA scores ($H = 2.70, p = 0.26$). This indicates that the format of work does not significantly influence burnout scores, suggesting that burnout risk may be consistent across different work arrangements.

To evaluate the extent to which age can predict scores in the next stage, a simple linear regression analysis was conducted, with the results summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. The Relationship Between Linear Regression Scores (EE, DEP, PA, Total) and Age

	df (model)	df (residuals)	F- statistic	p- value	R- squared	coeff const	coeff Age	lower conf. level	upper conf. level
Total	1	144	0.598	0.441	0.004	1.688	-0.011	-0.037	0.016
EE	1	144	0.552	0.459	0.004	1.582	0.012	-0.021	0.045
DEP	1	144	3.496	0.064	0.024	2.105	-0.035	-0.073	0.002
PA	1	144	0.365	0.547	0.003	1.376	-0.009	-0.037	0.019

The linear regression analysis indicates that age is not a significant predictor of burnout scores (Total, EE, DEP, PA). The high p-values across all models (> 0.05) suggest that there is no substantial relationship between age and any dimension of burnout.

There were five additional questions asked to all participants:

1. Money/Satisfaction: This question probed whether participants preferred work satisfaction over remuneration or remuneration over work satisfaction on a scale of 1 to 5. Response 1 indicated that subjects preferred remuneration over job satisfaction, whereas response 5 indicated that subjects preferred work satisfaction over remuneration.
2. Subjective salary: Here, we probed whether participants feel that they are adequately paid for their work on a scale of 1 to 3. Response 1 indicated that they felt they were underpaid, response 2 indicated that they were adequately paid, and response 3 indicated that they were well-paid.
3. Subjective physical health: This looked at how the participants felt about their physical health status on a scale of 1 to 5. Response 1 indicated that they felt that their physical health status was very bad, and response 5 indicated that they felt their physical health status was very good.
4. Managerial fairness: This question looked at the participants' perception of the fairness of their managers towards the employees on a scale of 1 to 5. Response 1 indicated that they felt their managers to be highly unfair towards employees, whereas response 5 indicated that they felt their managers to be very fair towards employees.
5. Freedom of expression: With this question, we studied how easily participants were able to express different opinions (personal or work-related) in the presence of their co-workers and supervisors on a scale of 1 to 3. Response 1 indicated that participants felt they could not express different opinions without negative consequences, response 2 indicated that participants felt they could express different opinions with caution, whereas response 3 indicated that participants felt they could express different opinions without fear of negative consequences.

The relationships between these five questions and the burnout scores (Total, EE, DEP, PA) as determined by ANOVA tests, are presented in Table 3. The analyses revealed that prioritizing job satisfaction over financial gain has a significant impact on total burnout scores ($H = 13.456$, $p = 0.009$). This trend was observed in the EE domain ($H = 11.813$, $p = 0.019$). Post-hoc analyses performed with Dunn's z-tests including Bonferroni corrections indicated that individuals who prioritized salary over job satisfaction, i.e., in

Group 1 (N = 74, mean = 1.57, SD = 0.47) showed higher total burnout scores compared to Group 4 (N = 31, mean = 1.18, SD = 0.54; z = 3.383, p = 0.007). Similar analyses on EE scores showed significant differences between scores of individuals in Group 1 (N = 74, mean = 2.08, SD = 0.58) and those in Group 4 (N = 31, mean = 1.61, SD = 0.75; z = 3.009, p = 0.026). No significant relation was found between this variable and the DEP scores (H = 7.15, p = 0.13) or the PA scores (H = 7.46, p = 0.11), indicating that the effect observed in the total score was mainly because of the effect in the EE scores.

Table 3. The Relationship Between ANOVA Test Scores (EE, DEP, PA, Total) and Income/Satisfaction, Subjective Salary, Subjective Physical Health, Subjective Psychological Health, Judging Bosses/Co-workers, and Freedom of Expression

	N	Total		EE		DEP		PA		
		Mean (std)	Statistic	Mean (std)	Statistic	Mean (std)	Statistic	Mean (std)	Statistic	
Money/Satisfaction	1	74	1.57 (0.47)	H = 13.46 (0.01)*	2.08 (0.58)	H = 11.81 (0.02)*	1.40 (0.76)	H = 7.15 (0.13)	1.24 (0.53)	H = 7.46 (0.11)
	2	30	1.37 (0.63)		1.76 (0.74)		1.13 (0.81)		1.21 (0.65)	
	3	6	1.39 (0.59)		1.63 (0.60)		1.30 (0.85)		1.25 (0.58)	
	4	31	1.18 (0.54)		1.61 (0.75)		1.01 (0.74)		0.93 (0.45)	
	5	5	1.35 (1.12)		1.69 (0.97)		1.16 (1.21)		1.20 (1.33)	
Subjective salary	1	91	1.59 (0.55)	F = 12.43 (<0.001)*	2.08 (0.63)	H = 21.04 (<0.001)*	1.44 (0.79)	H = 16.29 (<0.001)*	1.26 (0.60)	H = 8.03 (0.02)*
	2	47	1.21 (0.50)		1.60 (0.68)		0.97 (0.72)		1.07 (0.53)	
	3	8	0.90 (0.34)		1.31 (0.45)		0.65 (0.50)		0.75 (0.49)	
Subjective physical health	1	7	2.25 (0.41)	F = 13.98 (<0.001)*	2.71 (0.26)	H = 41.70 (<0.001)*	2.06 (0.75)	H = 19.14 (<0.001)*	1.96 (0.58)	H = 28.25 (<0.001)*
	2	29	1.74 (0.54)		2.29 (0.56)		1.44 (0.78)		1.49 (0.58)	
	3	37	1.55 (0.44)		2.01 (0.58)		1.45 (0.78)		1.19 (0.45)	
	4	53	1.21 (0.46)		1.68 (0.61)		1.03 (0.70)		0.94 (0.51)	
	5	20	1.06 (0.56)		1.31 (0.69)		0.89 (0.76)		0.99 (0.61)	
Managerial Fairness	1	13	1.92 (0.49)	F = 10.53 (<0.001)*	2.53 (0.38)	H = 39.81 (<0.001)*	1.51 (0.75)	H = 18.23 (<0.001)*	1.73 (0.62)	H = 18.54 (<0.001)*
	2	27	1.66 (0.45)		2.20 (0.53)		1.46 (0.82)		1.33 (0.45)	
	3	26	1.49 (0.50)		2.13 (0.53)		1.22 (0.68)		1.11 (0.57)	
	4	39	1.47 (0.53)		1.78 (0.61)		1.47 (0.81)		1.16 (0.62)	
	5	41	1.05 (0.51)		1.41 (0.70)		0.82 (0.69)		0.92 (0.49)	
Freedom of expression	1	15	1.79 (0.60)	F = 6.74 (<0.001)*	2.20 (0.64)	H = 13.11 (<0.001)*	1.49 (0.89)	H = 2.58 (0.28)	1.69 (0.62)	H = 12.47 (<0.001)*
	2	79	1.49 (0.53)		2.00 (0.62)		1.29 (0.79)		1.17 (0.54)	
	3	52	1.25 (0.55)		1.61 (0.72)		1.12 (0.77)		1.01 (0.57)	

* Significant relations.

Table 4 contains the absolute differences between mean scores for each group, with the significant differences highlighted in red. Our results indicate that those who place greater importance on job satisfaction compared to salary tend to report lower burnout levels through the emotional exhaustion spectrum.

Table 4. The Relationship Between the Independent Variables Importance of Earnings and Work Satisfaction and Burnout

Absolute differences: Total scores						Absolute differences: EE scores						Absolute differences: DEP scores						Absolute differences: PA scores									
Groups		1	2	3	4	5	Groups		1	2	3	4	5	Groups		1	2	3	4	5	Groups		1	2	3	4	5
1	0	0.21	0.18	0.39	0.22	0	0.32	0.45	0.47	0.39	0	0.27	0.1	0.39	0.24	0	0.03	0.01	0.31	0.04	0	0.03	0	0.04	0.28	0.01	
2	0.21	0	0.03	0.18	0.02	0.32	0	0.13	0.16	0.07	0.27	0	0.17	0.12	0.03	0.03	0	0.04	0.28	0.01	0.03	0	0.04	0.28	0.01		
3	0.18	0.03	0	0.21	0.04	0.45	0.13	0	0.02	0.06	0.1	0.17	0	0.29	0.14	0.01	0.04	0	0.32	0.05	0.01	0.04	0	0.32	0.05		
4	0.39	0.18	0.21	0	0.17	0.47	0.16	0.02	0	0.08	0.39	0.12	0.29	0	0.15	0.31	0.28	0.32	0	0.27	0.31	0.28	0.32	0	0.27		
5	0.22	0.02	0.04	0.17	0	0.39	0.07	0.06	0.08	0	0.24	0.03	0.14	0.15	0	0.04	0.01	0.05	0.27	0	0.04	0.01	0.05	0.27	0		

Independent variable: Work for money or satisfaction

We had observed a significant relationship between reported salary adequacy and total burnout scores ($F(2, 143) = 12.435, p < 0.001$), EE scores ($H = 21.036, p < 0.001$), DEP scores ($H = 16.291, p < 0.001$) and PA scores ($H = 8.025, p = 0.018$). Post-hoc analyses (standard t-tests for the total score, and Dunn's z-tests for the domain level scores) were performed with Bonferroni corrections to find significant pairwise relationships. Participants who felt they were inadequately compensated (Group 1, $N = 91$, mean = 1.59, $SD = 0.55$) had significantly higher total burnout scores than those who perceived their salaries as adequate (Group 2, $N = 47$, mean = 1.21, $SD = 0.50$; $t = 4.028, p < 0.001$) and those who perceived they were well-paid (Group 3, $N = 8$, mean = 0.90, $SD = 0.34$; $t = 3.568, p = 0.001$). This trend was also observed in the EE domain, with individuals in Group 1 ($N = 91$, mean = 2.08, $SD = 0.63$) having higher scores than individuals in Group 2 ($N = 47$, mean = 1.60, $SD = 0.68$; $z = 3.81, p < 0.001$) and individuals in Group 3 ($N = 8$, mean = 1.31, $SD = 0.45$; $z = 3.150, p = 0.005$), and in the DEP domain, with individuals in Group 1 ($N = 91$, mean = 1.44, $SD = 0.79$) having higher scores than individuals in Group 2 ($N = 47$, mean = 0.97, $SD = 0.72$; $z = 3.414, p = 0.002$) and individuals in Group 3 ($N = 8$, mean = 0.65, $SD = 0.50$; $z = 2.690, p = 0.021$). In the PA domain, the only significant pairwise comparison was between individuals in Group 1 ($N = 91$, mean = 1.26, $SD = 0.60$) and individuals in Group 3 ($N = 8$, mean = 0.75, $SD = 0.49$; $z = 2.474, p = 0.040$). The absolute differences between the scores of groups are provided in Table 5, with the significant differences highlighted. Our findings point to a strong association between perceived salary adequacy and emotional well-being.

Physical health perception was observed to be significantly indicative of the total burnout scores ($F(4, 141) = 13.978, p < 0.001$), as well as of the EE scores ($H = 41.697, p < 0.001$), DEP scores ($H = 19.143, p < 0.001$) and PA scores ($H = 28.255, p < 0.001$). We performed post-hoc analyses (standard t-tests for the total score, and Dunn's z-tests for the domain level scores) with Bonferroni corrections to find significant pairwise relationships.

Table 5. The Relationship Between the Independent Variable Adequacy of Earnings and Burnout

	Absolute differences: Total scores			Absolute differences: EE scores			Absolute differences: DEP scores			Absolute differences: PA scores		
Groups	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
1	0	0.38	0.69	0	0.48	0.77	0	0.48	0.79	0	0.18	0.51
2	0.38	0	0.31	0.48	0	0.29	0.48	0	0.32	0.18	0	0.32
3	0.69	0.31	0	0.77	0.29	0	0.79	0.32	0	0.51	0.32	0
	Groups			Groups			Groups			Groups		

Independent variable: Perceived salary adequacy

About half the pairwise comparisons were significant, indicating that this variable is a significant factor in detecting burnout levels. For ease of readability, we split reporting them by domain (total, EE, DEP, and PA):

- Total: Respondents with a poor sense of physical health (Group 1, N = 7, mean = 2.25, SD = 0.41) reported significantly higher total burnout scores than those with better physical health perceptions including Group 3 (N = 37, mean = 1.55, SD = 0.44; t = 3.480, p = 0.007), Group 4 (N = 53, mean = 1.21, SD = 0.46; t = 5.290, p < 0.001) and Group 5 (N = 20, mean = 1.06, SD = 0.56; t = 5.554, p < 0.001). Individuals in Group 2 (N = 29, mean = 1.74, SD = 0.54) reported significantly higher total scores when compared to individuals in Group 4 (t = 4.698, p < 0.001) and individuals in Group 5 (t = 4.805, p < 0.001). Finally, individuals in Group 3 reported significantly higher total scores compared to individuals in Group 4 (t = 3.235, p = 0.015) and individuals in Group 5 (t = 3.619, p = 0.004).
- EE: Significant differences were found between individuals in Group 1 (N = 7, mean = 2.71, SD = 0.26) and individuals in Group 3 (N = 37, mean = 2.01, SD = 0.58; z = 2.841, p = 0.045), individuals in Group 4 (N = 53, mean = 1.68, SD = 0.61; z = 4.102, p < 0.001), and individuals in Group 5 (N = 20, mean = 1.31, SD = 0.69; z = 4.771, p < 0.001). Individuals in Group 2 (N = 29, mean = 2.29, SD = 0.56) had higher EE scores than individuals in Group 4 (z = 4.082, p < 0.001) and individuals in Group 5 (z = 4.776, p < 0.001). Finally, individuals in Group 3 had higher EE scores than those in Group 5 (z = 3.330, p = 0.009).
- DEP: Individuals in Group 1 (N = 7, mean = 2.06, SD = 0.75) had significantly higher DEP burnout scores than those in Group 4 (N = 53, mean = 1.03, SD = 0.70; z = 3.053, p = 0.023) and Group 5 (N = 20, mean = 0.89, SD = 0.76; z = 3.255, p = 0.011).
- PA: Significant differences were found with individuals in Group 1 (N = 7, mean = 1.96, SD = 0.58) having significantly higher PA scores than those in Group 4 (N = 53, mean = 0.94, SD = 0.51; z = 3.864, p = 0.001) and those in Group 5 (N = 20, mean = 0.99, SD = 0.61; z = 3.363, p = 0.008). Individuals in Group 2 (N = 29, mean = 1.49, SD = 0.58) also had significantly higher PA than those in Group 4 (z = 4.059, p < 0.001) and Group 5 (z = 2.960, p = 0.031).

Table 6 shows the absolute differences of the scores between groups with the significant differences highlighted in red. These results support the idea that physical health perception is essential in detecting burnout symptoms.

Table 6. The Relationship Between the Independent Variable Sense of Physical Health and Burnout

		Absolute differences: Total scores					Absolute differences: EE scores					Absolute differences: DEP scores					Absolute differences: PA scores				
Groups		Groups					Groups					Groups					Groups				
		1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
1		0	0.51	0.7	1	1.2	0	0.43	0.7	1	1.4	0	0.62	0.61	1	1.2	0	0.47	0.78	1	0.97
2		0.51	0	0.19	0.53	0.68	0.43	0	0.28	0.61	0.98	0.62	0	0.01	0.41	0.55	0.47	0	0.3	0.55	0.5
3		0.7	0.19	0	0.34	0.49	0.7	0.28	0	0.33	0.71	0.61	0.01	0	0.42	0.56	0.78	0.3	0	0.25	0.2
4		1	0.53	0.34	0	0.15	1	0.61	0.33	0	0.37	1	0.41	0.42	0	0.14	1	0.55	0.25	0	0.06
5		1.2	0.68	0.49	0.15	0	1.4	0.98	0.71	0.37	0	1.2	0.55	0.56	0.14	0	0.97	0.5	0.2	0.06	0

Independent variable: Perceived physical health condition

Managerial fairness was additionally found to be a significant factor in explaining the total burnout scores ($F(4, 141) = 10.529, p < 0.001$), EE scores ($H = 39.813, p < 0.001$), DEP scores ($H = 18.227, p = 0.001$) and PA scores ($H = 18.540, p < 0.001$). To further understand the underlying effect, we performed post-hoc analyses (standard t-tests for the total scores, and Dunn's z-tests for the domain scores) with Bonferroni corrections to identify significant pairwise comparisons. We found that respondents who rated their managers as fair, i.e., in Group 5 ($N = 41, \text{mean} = 1.05, \text{SD} = 0.51$) experienced significantly lower total burnout levels compared to those in Group 1 ($N = 13, \text{mean} = 1.92, \text{SD} = 0.49; t = 5.440, p < 0.001$), Group 2 ($N = 27, \text{mean} = 1.66, \text{SD} = 0.45; t = 4.915, p < 0.001$), Group 3 ($N = 26, \text{mean} = 1.49, \text{SD} = 0.50; t = 3.451, p = 0.007$) and Group 4 ($N = 39, \text{mean} = 1.47, \text{SD} = 0.53; t = 3.723, p = 0.003$). Similar trends were observed across the three domains. Individuals in Group 5 ($N = 41, \text{mean} = 1.41, \text{SD} = 0.70$) had lower EE burnout scores than individuals in Group 1 ($N = 13, \text{mean} = 2.53, \text{SD} = 0.38; z = 5.134, p < 0.001$), Group 2 ($N = 27, \text{mean} = 2.20, \text{SD} = 0.53; z = 4.420, p < 0.001$) and Group 3 ($N = 26, \text{mean} = 2.13, \text{SD} = 0.53; z = 3.850, p = 0.001$). Respondents in Group 4 ($N = 39, \text{mean} = 1.78, \text{SD} = 0.61$) also had significantly lower EE scores than those in Group 1 ($z = 3.780, p = 0.002$). When looking at the DEP scores, we found that burnout scores for subjects in Group 5 ($N = 41, \text{mean} = 0.82, \text{SD} = 0.69$) were significantly lower than those in Group 1 ($N = 13, \text{mean} = 1.51, \text{SD} = 0.75; z = 2.835, p = 0.046$), Group 2 ($N = 27, \text{mean} = 1.46, \text{SD} = 0.82; z = 3.237, p = 0.012$) and Group 4 ($N = 39, \text{mean} = 1.47, \text{SD} = 0.81; z = 3.592, p = 0.003$). Pairwise comparisons between the PA scores indicated that respondents in Group 5 ($N = 41, \text{mean} = 0.92, \text{SD} = 0.49$) had significantly lower scores than those in Group 1 ($N = 13, \text{mean} = 1.73, \text{SD} = 0.62; z = 3.889, p = 0.001$) and Group 2 ($N = 27, \text{mean} = 1.33, \text{SD} = 0.45; z = 2.918, p = 0.035$).

Table 7 lists the differences between burnout scores between all pairwise comparisons with the significant pairs highlighted in red. Our results indicate that perceived fairness in management has a direct impact on employee burnout. We also found freedom of expression to be a significant variable in detecting total scores ($F(2, 143) = 6.743, p = 0.002$), EE scores ($H = 13.114, p = 0.001$), and PA scores ($H = 12.467, p = 0.002$). No significant relationship was found between this variable and the DEP scores ($H = 2.577, p = 0.276$). Therefore, we performed post-hoc analyses (standard t-tests for the total score, and Dunn's z-tests for the EE and PA scores) with Bonferroni corrections for multiple comparisons.

Table 7. The Relationship Between the Independent Variable Assessment of Supervisor Fairness and Burnout

When looking at the total scores, we found that participants who felt empowered to express their opinions freely, i.e., in Group 3 (N = 52, mean = 1.25, SD = 0.55) had significantly lower burnout scores than those in more “restrictive” environments, i.e., in Group 1 (N = 15, mean = 1.79, SD = 0.60; $t = 3.440, p = 0.002$) and in Group 2 (N = 79, mean = 1.49, SD = 0.53; $t = 2.460, p = 0.045$). The analysis on EE scores highlighted a similar trend with respondents in Group 3 (N = 52, mean = 1.61, SD = 0.72) having significantly lower EE scores than those in Group 1 (N = 15, mean = 2.20, SD = 0.64; $z = 3.038, p = 0.007$) and Group 2 (N = 79, mean = 2.00, SD = 0.62; $z = 2.949, p = 0.010$). Finally, we found that the individuals in Group 1 (N = 15, mean = 1.69, SD = 0.62) had significantly higher PA scores than those in Group 2 (N = 79, mean = 1.17, SD = 0.54; $z = 2.669, p = 0.023$) and those in Group 3 (N = 52, mean = 1.01, SD = 0.57; $z = 3.519, p = 0.001$).

The absolute differences between all pairwise comparisons for the total and domain-level scores are provided in Table 8, with the significant comparisons highlighted in red. These findings underscore the importance of a supportive workplace culture, emphasizing open communication, as a critical factor in mitigating burnout.

Table 8. The Relationship Between the Independent Variable Freedom to Express Different Opinions and Burnout

5. Discussion

The findings of this study offer significant insights into the multifaceted and context-dependent nature of burnout among young professionals in Poland. The data confirm and

extend previous empirical research by illustrating that burnout is less a consequence of immutable personal traits and more a reflection of organizational dynamics, socio-economic perceptions, and relational contexts.

A pivotal outcome of the study is the salience of subjective perceptions over objective conditions. For instance, while actual salary levels showed no statistically significant association with burnout scores, the perceived adequacy of income emerged as a robust predictor across all dimensions of burnout. This aligns with the growing body of research emphasizing the role of cognitive appraisal in occupational stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). In other words, it is not the financial condition itself, but how it is interpreted and internalized by the individual that contributes to emotional exhaustion and diminished professional efficacy.

Similarly, managerial fairness and freedom of expression surfaced as significant psychosocial buffers against burnout. These findings corroborate theoretical models such as the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) framework (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007), which posits that perceived organizational support acts as a crucial resource that mitigates the deleterious effects of job demands. The correlation between perceived justice and lower burnout scores- particularly in emotional exhaustion and personal accomplishment-underscores the psychological contract between employer and employee. When this contract is breached, as in cases of perceived unfairness or censorship, the risk of disengagement escalates.

Moreover, the observed relationship between civil status and burnout- where single individuals report significantly higher burnout levels than their partnered counterparts-raises important considerations regarding the role of social capital and emotional support systems. This finding substantiates previous studies (e.g., Hobfoll, 1989), which suggest that the availability of interpersonal resources, particularly in intimate contexts, can function as a protective buffer against occupational stress.

An intriguing aspect of the data is the non-significant relationship between gender and burnout, which diverges from certain strands of literature suggesting a higher prevalence of burnout among women in caring professions (Purvanova & Muros, 2010). This discrepancy may be attributed to the relatively homogeneous professional backgrounds and life stages of the sample group, which could have attenuated gender-based differences in work-related experiences.

Importantly, perceived physical health emerged as a strong correlate of burnout, spanning all subdimensions. This finding accentuates the bidirectional relationship between physical and psychological well-being a dynamic extensively documented in occupational health literature (Melamed et al., 2006). Diminished physical health perceptions may not only signal physiological strain but also reflect a broader depletion of personal resources, as described in Conservation of Resources Theory (Hobfoll, 1989).

The implications of these findings are both theoretical and practical. Theoretically, they reinforce a socio-organizational perspective of burnout, emphasizing that structural conditions and relational climates are more predictive than static personal variables. Building on this, the paper could further benefit from integrating perspectives developed in psychosocial risk studies (e.g., Dejours, 2009; Eurofound & EU-OSHA, 2014), critical management studies (e.g., Alvesson & Willmott, 2003), and the psychodynamics of work (e.g., Clot, 2010; Dejours, 1998). These approaches offer valuable insight into how systemic organizational demands, ideological pressures, and unconscious emotional mechanisms shape burnout. They also question how modern managerial practices, often

grounded in control and instrumental rationality, might deepen emotional exhaustion and depersonalization among workers. Including such perspectives can support a more holistic, critical understanding of burnout that reaches beyond individual resilience models. Practically, they highlight areas where targeted interventions could have the greatest impact—namely, cultivating just managerial practices, enabling open dialogue within teams, and acknowledging the subjective realities of workers' financial and physical conditions.

In sum, this study advances a nuanced understanding of burnout by foregrounding the interaction between subjective experiences and organizational conditions. It calls for a paradigmatic shift in burnout prevention— from individual- focused resilience training to system- level reforms that promote equity, voice, and meaning at work.

To further reinforce this approach and address potential oversimplifications in the individualist–organizational dichotomy, it is essential to more clearly articulate the theoretical framework underpinning the study's conception of burnout. While the research is positioned within an organizational paradigm, it also implicitly aligns with a broader literature that understands burnout not only as a reaction to job demands, but as a reflection of the deeper psychological and symbolic relationship between individuals and their work.

In this regard, the study incorporates elements of the growing field of meaningful work, which highlights the importance of autonomy, value congruence, and social contribution in sustaining well-being and preventing burnout (Lips-Wiersma & Morris, 2009; Rosso et al., 2010). Rather than treating burnout exclusively as a product of extrinsic job characteristics, this perspective emphasizes its emergence as a response to a loss of existential coherence—a condition where individuals struggle to find significance in what they do (Pines & Aronson, 1988; Steger et al., 2012).

Accordingly, organizational factors such as fairness, freedom of expression, and income adequacy—used in this study as predictors—can also be interpreted as indicators of the degree to which work is experienced as meaningful. For instance, perceived injustice may not only elicit stress but also undermine one's sense of purpose and recognition. Similarly, environments that suppress voice and autonomy may impair employees' ability to express their identity through work, thus deepening emotional detachment and exhaustion.

Therefore, this study implicitly adopts a dual lens—one that integrates both structural-organizational and symbolic-existential dimensions of burnout. While it focuses empirically on organizational predictors, it opens conceptual space for future research to directly explore the content and meaning of work, and to examine how burnout may stem from a crisis of meaning rather than merely from an overload of demands.

Incorporating this broader theoretical orientation not only enhances the study's conceptual depth but also pre-empts potential critiques that the analysis neglects internal motivational and psychological dimensions. It affirms that burnout, as a multifaceted phenomenon, must be addressed through system-level reforms that cultivate not just resilience, but recognition, justice, and meaningful engagement.

6. Conclusion

This study emphasizes that burnout is a complex issue influenced by both organizational practices and personal factors, with significant effects on young professionals. While burnout is often attributed to individual characteristics, our findings indicate that organizational support and socio-economic factors are equally critical. Key

determinants such as salary satisfaction, managerial fairness, and perceived physical health highlight the importance of addressing both structural and cultural factors in the workplace.

An environment that promotes fair compensation, equitable management, and freedom of expression was found to be strongly associated with lower levels of burnout. Participants who felt their salaries were adequate and perceived their managers as fair had significantly lower burnout scores, underscoring the value of good pay, fair management practices and supportive policies. Additionally, employees who feel that they could express their opinions freely had lower burnout scores, suggesting that a culture of open communication and willingness to accept others' ideas could play a crucial role in preventing burnout.

The research demonstrates that perceived physical health and financial well-being are fundamental in managing burnout. Participants reporting better physical health and salary satisfaction exhibited resilience against burnout symptoms. Furthermore, marital status also affected burnout; single individuals experienced higher levels of burnout compared to their partnered peers. This finding gives weight to the idea that social and economic support might function as protective factors.

Our results that burnout is not just an individual problem but also linked to organizational structures is supported by numerous sources in the literature. For example, Maslach and Leiter (2016), note that burnout is linked to organizational factors such as injustice and lack of support in the workplace. Understanding the impact of organizational context and workplace culture on burnout is essential for developing effective preventive strategies.

Future research should examine burnout over time and across various industries to identify the causal effects of organizational and socio-economic factors. These findings support the implementation of fair compensation, managerial justice, and psychological safety in organizations, thereby enhancing employee resilience, satisfaction, and overall well-being.

The implementation of training and development programs might be needed to reduce burnout. As Luthans (2011), stated, providing employees with training in stress management and personal development can enhance their capacity to maintain both physical and psychological health. Such programs, particularly aimed at helping young professionals understand and cope with workplace challenges, can play a significant role in reducing their risk of experiencing burnout.

In conclusion, it is essential for organizations to create a more inclusive and equitable work culture to reduce burnout experiences among young adults. Supporting employees in establishing a healthy work-life balance, as highlighted by Greenhaus & Allen, 2010, emerges as an effective strategy for reducing burnout. Additionally, ensuring that employees feel psychologically safe at work will enhance their motivation and commitment, contributing to organizational productivity.

Considering these findings, managers and organizations might need to take necessary steps to reduce burnout. As suggested by Schaufeli (2017), a range of policies and practices can be developed and implemented to ensure the long-term success of both individuals and organizations. Enabling employees to work in a healthy environment is essential for sustainable success at both individual and organizational levels.

Finally, further research and literature development are needed to deepen our understanding of the multidimensional nature of burnout and to formulate effective

intervention strategies. By adopting a holistic approach to the burnout issue, we can enhance the success and satisfaction of young adults in their professional lives. Addressing burnout issues should be considered critical for improving the health and well-being of both individuals and organizations.

Despite of this study provides valuable insights into the organizational determinants of burnout, it is important to highlight some limitations. Firstly, the use of a 4-point Likert scale- although effective in reducing cognitive load and improving response clarity- may have limited the sensitivity and granularity of participants' responses. Secondly, the sample, which consists solely of young Polish professionals, restricts the generalizability of the findings across different cultural and age groups.

7. References

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